

ANALYTIC SIMULATION OF MOTORCYCLE COMPOSITE HELMETS BEHAVIOUR UNDER IMPACT

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ABSTRACT

The problem of the response of a composite motorcycle helmet during impact is approached. It is shown that the entire history of impact can be analytically simulated by a two-degrees-of-freedom model; however, if only the maximum acceleration occurring during impact must be known, as usually happens in tests carried out according to international standards, a simple procedure, not accounting for vibrational effects, can be reliably used.

INTRODUCTION

According to the European rules for motorcycle helmets testing, a helmet is put on a wood head, 5 kg in mass, and let to fall on an semispherical steel tup from a 2.5 m height (fig. 1a); a 300 g acceleration, as measured by a transducer placed within the wood head, must not be exceeded in order to satisfy the standard.

Fig.1. Impact test on a helmet; a) Schematic view; b) two-degrees-of-freedom model.

The impact phenomenon is quite complicated to be modeled by simple analytical tools: the external shell, generally made of polycarbonate or composite materials, is geometrically characterized by a double curvature and exhibits under impact a nonlinear behaviour; moreover, also the material supporting the external shell, frequently foamed polystyrene, is highly nonlinear; finally, the contact

laws governing both the tup-shell and the shell-foam interactions can be hardly described by mathematical relations.

In this work the problem is approached by analytical tools; it is shown that a relatively simple solution can be found, especially when, as generally happens in standard tests, only the maximum acceleration occurring during impact is wanted.

ANALYTICAL MODEL

As a first approach to the problem, the test conditions described above can be reduced to the two-degrees-of-freedom model depicted in fig. 1b: m_1, m_2 represent the wood head and shell mass, respectively, whereas the spring constant k_2 accounts for the tup behaviour; the spring constant k_1 simulates the response of the tup-shell-foam system, so that it is expected to be highly nonlinear.

The model of fig. 1b can be easily solved in a symbolic form; by putting:

$$k_i = \frac{F_i}{s_i} \quad (1)$$

and applying D'Alembert theorem to m_1 and m_2 :

$$m_1 \frac{d^2 s_1}{dt^2} + k_1 (s_1 - s_2) = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$m_2 \frac{d^2 s_2}{dt^2} + (k_1 + k_2) s_2 - k_1 s_1 = 0 \quad (3)$$

In eqs (1) to (3), F_i indicates the force acting on the i -th spring, s_i the displacement of the mass m_i and t is time. By solving eqs (2), (3) in terms of the unknown displacements s_i , a solution to the approached problem can be obtained. It is important to note that eqs (2), (3) are valid for both linear and nonlinear springs, provided k_i is given by eq. (1); however while a closed form solution can be found [1] in the linear case (constant k_i), in the nonlinear one numerical methods are to be adopted. Moreover, an explicit relation for k_1 , modelling the tup-shell-foam interaction, must be established; in order to do this, some simplifying hypotheses were adopted in the present work:

- the helmet shell was approximated by a flat, linear elastic, circular plate; curvature effects, possible boundary effects and failures occurring in the shell during impact were disregarded. This hypothesis is not acceptable for polycarbonate shells, which exhibit a highly nonlinear behaviour; limiting the attention to composite shells, however, the plate linearity is expected to be maintained at least in the first part of the s-e curve;

- the force resulting from the contact between the shell and the tup was imagined as concentrated; the effect of the tup actual radius of curvature on the tup-shell-foam response was not accounted for.

Under these hypotheses, the problem reduces to the one of a linear elastic, circular plate on a nonlinear foundation, subjected to a concentrated load; to solve it, a method similar to that proposed in [2] for the linear elastic case, based on energy considerations, was adopted. The analytical relations driving to the final solution are not discussed here in detail; only the main features of the technique are briefly recalled.

A second order polynomial was arbitrarily assumed for the plate deflection s :

$$s = A + Br^2 \quad (4)$$

where A, B are two unknown constants and r the distance from the point of load application. Putting $s = 0$ in eq. (4), the radius r^* along which a contact exists between the plate and the foundation was calculated:

$$r^* = \square \left(-\frac{A}{B} \right) \quad (5)$$

The total potential energy U_t of the system was evaluated as the sum of the strain energy of the foundation, the strain energy of the plate and the potential energy of the applied load. In calculating U_t , a fifth order polynomial was adopted to fit the s - e curve of the foundation; only the plate portion enclosed within the radius r^* was assumed to contribute to the strain energy. In this way, an explicit equation correlating U_t to the unknown constants A, B , the external load F , the plate flexural rigidity D and the foundation thickness, t_f , and mechanical behaviour, M_f , was found:

$$U_t = f(A, B, F, D, t_f, M_f) \quad (6)$$

By applying the principle of minimum energy, the derivatives of eq. (6) with respect to A, B were taken and equated to zero, obtaining two equations; by them, the unknown A, B were finally calculated by numerical methods. It was therefore possible to evaluate the variation of the spring constant, k_1 , as a function of the spring displacement.

Both the method described above and eqs (2), (3) were implemented in the computer program IMPACT, where eqs. (2), (3) were solved by finite differences.

MATERIALS AND TEST METHODS

In order to experimentally verify the analytical model, two different series of tests were carried out. The first series was aimed to validate the model simulating the tup-shell-foam interaction: 160 mm \times 160 mm flat plates, made by both glass and kevlar fabric reinforced polyester, were put on a foamed polystyrene substrate 0.045 g/cm³ in density and 30mm in thickness, resting on a concrete floor, and struck by a falling semispherical tup 40 mm in radius and 8.23 kg in mass. The resin content by volume in the composite plates was \square 35%. Impact history was taken by an accelerometer placed into the tup, recorded and treated by standard algorithms [3] to obtain the force-displacement curve. To compare the experimental results with theoretical predictions, the plates as well as foam mechanical behaviour was characterized: flexure tests were performed on the composites, and their static flexural stiffness was adopted in the calculations; this was justified by previous results [4], which showed no evidence of viscoelastic phenomena on the Young's modulus of a laminate. Both static and dynamic compression tests were carried out on the foam; in this case also, only a negligible effect of the loading rate was observed on the s - e curve of the material; therefore, any information provided by static s - e curves was used in the dynamic model.

In a second series of tests, glass fiber reinforced plastic helmets were subjected to impact on their top, following European standards. In this case, the impact history, under form of force-time curve, was taken by an accelerometric system put within the wood head and sent to a chart recorder.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In fig. 2, two curves obtained in impact tests carried out on flat plates put on foamed polystyrene resting on a concrete floor are shown; the acceleration a , which is the most important parameter to be controlled according to European standards, is reported against the tup displacement s . Full points refer to experimental data, whereas continuous lines represent analytical predictions. Only loading curves have been reported in fig. 2: although the proposed model may predict impact

history during loading as well as unloading, to calculate the latter the s-e curve of foam during unloading had to be known; this was beyond the scope of the present work.

It is essentially observed from fig. 2 that theoretical predictions tend to slightly overestimate the initial system rigidity; nevertheless, the correlation between theory and experiments is quite good, and both maximum acceleration and maximum displacement can be correctly evaluated by theory. Although some delamination damage was observed in the plstes after test, these results suggest that in fact the loss of plate rigidity due to failures during impact has a very limited effect on the whole response of the structure under examination; of course, it is expected that different conclusions could be drawn if tups with small radii of curvature were used. Also the actual distribution of the load on the plate face during contact seems to be of minor importance in affecting the impact history.

In testing the validity of the oscillatory model expressed by eqs. (2), (3), a difficulty arose due to the unknown value of the constant k_2 , determined by the tup rigidity; although the order of magnitude of k_2 was grossly evaluated as $\approx 10^6$ N/mm, an exact measurement could not be carried out, because the actual load distribution on the tup during impact was of course unknown. With the aim of studying the effect of k_2 on the response of the system under examination, a parametric study was then performed, by assuming $m_1 = 5$ kg, $m_2 = 1.8$ Kg, and varying k_2 in the range $10^2 - 10^6$ N/mm, k_1 was calculated by the tup-shell-foam interaction model, putting the foam thickness $t_f = 30$ mm and the shell flexural rigidity $D = 33.8 \times 10^3$ Nmm. Finally, the impact speed was assumed to be $V_0 = 7$ m/s. It is worth noting that all the values used in the analysis are typical of the real case. In facing the oscillatory problem, different hypotheses on the foam behaviour during unloading were done, in order to ascertain its importance on the overall response of the structure; it was found that the acceleration-time curve was by no way affected by the foam behaviour during unloading, except in its last part, which is of no importance from a practical point of view. It was concluded that the knowledge of the foam behaviour during unloading was of limited importance for the examined problem.

Fig. 2 - Tup acceleration, a, vs. tup displacement, s, for two composite plates on foamed poly-

styrene. Continuous line: theoretical; full points; experimental.

Fig. 3 - Calculated maximum acceleration, a_{max} , vs. tup spring constant, k_2 .

Fig.4 - Acceleration-time curve for a glass-polyester helmet. Continuous line: theoretical; full points: experimental.

In fig. 3 the calculated maximum acceleration a_{max} is shown against k_2 . It can be seen that the maximum acceleration is strongly dependent on the k_2 real value in the field $10^2 - 10^3$ N/mm; in particular, a more compliant tup gives rise to lower a_{max} . However, for sufficiently stiff tups, a_{max} becomes independent of k_2 , approximating a limit value, indicated by the horizontal line in the

figure: this value corresponds to the one obtained by the tup-shell-foam interaction model, which does not account for the presence of the spring k_2 . It can be concluded that, if only the maximum acceleration occurring during impact is wanted, the latter model can be reliably used, without resorting to the two-degrees-of freedom model depicted in fig. 1a.

Of course, if the entire impact history has to be known, vibrational effects deriving from the presence of the tup cannot be disregarded. The effectiveness of the vibrational model in fig. 1a must be therefore experimentally verified. In fig. 4 the acceleration-time history recorded during an impact test, carried out by striking on the top a glass fiber reinforced polyester helmet according to European standards, is shown by full points; continuous line represents the theoretical prediction based on the model discussed above. Although some shift toward longer times is observed for the theoretical curve, partially justified by the approximations done for the foam unloading curve, in general a quite good agreement is verified between theory and experiments. In particular, the calculated maximum acceleration is very close to the measured one, and the complete shape of the real curve is very well fitted by the proposed model. Recalling that the theoretical model does not account for the actual curvature of the helmet shell, it can be also inferred that the helmet shape has a limited influence on the helmet response.

CONCLUSIONS

A vibrational model, aimed to simulate the behaviour of a motorcycle helmet subjected to impact, has been experimentally verified. Comparisons between theory and experimental results show good agreement between theoretical predictions and measured values. From the hypotheses on which the model relies, it can be concluded that the failures occurring in the helmet shell (made by composite materials) during impact affect in a limited way the overall response of the structure; also the actual load distribution during tup-shell interaction, as well as the shell curvature, seem to be of minor importance. Finally, when a sufficiently stiff tup is used to test a helmet (as happens in the case of European standards), information on the maximum acceleration can be supplied by a simplified model, simulating the tup-shell-foam interaction, but not accounting for vibrational effects.

Some limitation of the presented procedure are implicit in the hypotheses adopted to simplify the analytical solution. It is expected that the model will lose its applicability for tups characterized by small radii of curvature, because in this case the damage in the shell material will result in significant loss of rigidity; on the other hand, no information can be obtained from the analytical model on the stresses induced in the shell by impact, because the shell deformed shape is described by a second order polynomial, which can be only useful when the macroscopic response of the system is wanted [2]. The hypothesis of linear elastic behaviour of the shell is not acceptable in the case of polycarbonate, so that the tup-shell-foam interaction model can be used only for composite helmets. Finally, the model will fail in simulating the helmet behaviour when an impact near the boundary region of the structure is considered; in this case, the hypotheses of circular plate is directly called in question.

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